

STRENGTHENING LEARNING OUTCOMES THROUGH STUDENTS WORKING WITH QUIZZES

C. Posselt, C.S. Flyger and N.C. Kjaersgaard¹

Technical University of Denmark

Department of Engineering Technology and Didactics

Ballerup, Denmark

Conference Key Areas: *Student Engagement*

Keywords: *Strengthening learning outcome, engaging students, quizzes*

ABSTRACT

Most instructors of engineering students will be familiar with students who – instead of engaging actively with a given field of knowledge – merely reproduce the curriculum at the exam. This study hypothesizes that students will achieve a higher taxonomic level of learning outcome by using a didactic tool – with a higher degree of understanding, application, and reflection as a result. We have developed such a didactic tool, Quizry, to create engaging teaching sessions through a special learning process: students producing quizzes for one another.

¹ Corresponding author:

N.C. Kjaersgaard

nckj@dtu.dk

Orchid: 0000-0001-9486-7593

We applied the French researcher Guy Brousseau's theory of didactical situations in teaching and his five phases as a theoretical basis for our study. In the first phase, the didactic contract is established between the students and the instructor, i.e. the assignment of producing quizzes is handed over. During phases 2-4, the students work with the concrete quizzes (a-didactic parts), and lastly in phase 5, recap, cohesion of learning and transfer is established.

We examined the relationship between producing quizzes and student learning outcomes through the lens of the American professor Vincent Tinto's influential three-fold model of motivation: self-efficacy, sense of belonging and perception of curriculum. The students' self-efficacy and perception of curriculum are strengthened by working with the topic several times.

Among other things, the study showed that 79% of the respondents reported that preparing quizzes for other students improved their learning outcome compared to traditional learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Most instructors of engineering students will be familiar with students who – instead of engaging actively with a given field of knowledge in class and as preparation for class – merely reproduce the curriculum at the exam [1]. This often leads to low learning outcomes and subsequently to poor grades. Furthermore, research has shown that students tend to quite rapidly forget knowledge acquired in this way: a dissatisfactory learning result for students, instructors and institutions of higher education alike. This study hypothesizes that students will achieve a higher taxonomic level of learning outcome by using a didactic tool, hereafter known as Quizry – with a higher degree of understanding, application, and reflection as a result [2]. We have developed Quizry to create engaging teaching sessions through a special learning process, i.e. students producing quizzes for one another.

We applied the French mathematics didactician Guy Brousseau's theory of didactical situations in mathematics [3], according to which teaching situations may be divided into five phases. In the first phase, devolution, the didactic contract is established between the students and the instructor, the academic problem is handed over, and the students accept the responsibility.

Phases 2-4 are generally about the students being engaged in activities. In our study, the students are preparing multiple choice quizzes, both individually and in groups, and they answer the quiz questions individually. In phase 5, institutionalization, the results from phases 2-4 are collected. This activity took the form of a joint recap of the students' answers to the quiz questions.

In our study, we examined the relationship between Quizry and student learning outcomes through the lens of Vincent Tinto's influential three-fold model of motivation: self-efficacy, sense of belonging and perception of curriculum [4]. Furthermore, we examined the relationship between Quizry and student learning.

The students' self-efficacy is strengthened by working with the topic several times [4]. The group work with the preparation of the quizzes can help to strengthen the students' sense of belonging. In addition, if students experience the work with the quizzes as meaningful, it can strengthen their perception of curriculum.

The washback effect, which has been described by several theorists, e.g. [5], says that the purpose of participating in a course, for many students, is to a large extent to be able to pass the exam with a satisfying result. By having the students prepare quiz questions for each topic, the students are forced to reflect on what they have learned, which can contribute to avoid simple reproduction.

1.2 The didactical tool Quizry

Initially we contemplated methods for engaging students more inside and outside class, enhancing their learning outcomes. Thus being able to apply and transfer that knowledge and these competencies much more easily and qualified later in their study programmes as well as eventually in their professional lives as engineers. Based on our reflections, the idea of students producing quizzes emerged. We decided on developing and implementing a study process involving quiz work as part of preparation for class and as a didactical tool in class. In addition to implementing Quizry in different study programmes, we also had the opportunity to simultaneously conduct a systematic study of how to strengthen students' learning outcomes by using Quizry.

The basic idea is, as mentioned, to engage students through quiz work and to make the students do the work, as this often results in better learning processes and outcomes [6]. For this purpose, all students are part of a quiz-group, and the quiz-groups have different tasks at each teaching session.

At the end of each teaching topic the students worked on Quizry:

Before teaching sessions all students prepare for class as usual; however, in addition we ask them individually to bring to class one quiz question with at least three plausible, valid answers and one possible answer should be the better answer.

During the teaching sessions, the students first discuss the quality of their individual questions/answers in their quiz-groups; second agree on one quiz question/answers; and third send that question to a so-called quiz-responsible group. The task of the quiz-responsible group is to produce the quiz for the teaching session, and in doing

so they decide which questions/answers to use, modify and add. All quiz-groups are at one point during the semester responsible for producing a quiz. Quizzes consist of 10 questions/answers, and the quiz-responsible group makes sure that there are sufficient questions/answers.

Figure 1: Overview of the Quizry learning process

The study was conducted in the autumn semester 2020 at Technical University of Denmark in three different BEng courses across two study programmes. Quizry was used in two subject areas: managerial economics and cultural understanding in the 2nd and 4th semester. A total of 76 students participated in the courses. Due to the pandemic, we partly experienced lockdown, students being tested positive for COVID-19, online teaching and online exams, which complicated the data collection.

1.3 Hypothesis

The study hypothesis is that students who work with quizzes will strengthen their competencies of understanding, applying and analyzing within selected topics in different disciplines.

We expect that the teamwork will result in a positive impact on students' perception of curriculum, self-efficacy and sense of belonging alike. In addition, we anticipate that the students' learning outcome will reach the highest level in connection with their teamwork on their own concrete, specific quiz.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Methodology

During the study, we have collected various qualitative data through questionnaires answered by the involved students and undertaken indirect participant observations by instructors.

We have chosen the questionnaire format as it gave an opportunity to receive anonymous answers, so that students did not have to worry about giving very honest answers/opinions of the learning process or other concerns. The questionnaire consisted of five open-ended questions and one closed question regarding quality of learning with the categories "Yes, better", "Yes, however, almost the same" or "No". At

the end of each Quizry, each student in the quiz-responsible group individually answered a questionnaire; furthermore time was set aside for all students to answer a questionnaire of self-reflection on their learning outcome.

Besides the questionnaires, we decided to use covert indirect participant observations during the Quizry process. We chose covert observations in order not to influence the learning process itself and not to affect the answers of the questionnaires. As for indirect observations, we observed the students' behaviour during the Quizry process in class. As a result of our positions as instructors, we became participants in the Quizry process.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Quantative and qualitative results

We have systematically researched and evaluated the students' perception of their own learning in connection with the use of the Quizry. Each student from the 10 quiz-responsible groups was asked to answer a survey regarding their learning. The overall results are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Overall results from surveys.

Group	Answers	Enhanced learning through quiz work		
		Yes, improved substantially	Yes, slightly	No improvement
1	2	1		1
2	5	2	3	
3	5	3	2	
4	3			3
5	4	3	1	
6	4	2	1	1
7	3	2		1
8	4	2		2
9	3	1	2	
10	4	2	2	
	37	18	11	8
In %		49%	30%	22%

We received a total of 37 answers in the three different courses. 79% of the respondents answered that preparing quizzes for the other students improved their learning outcome compared to traditional learning. As the table shows, 49% state that their improvement was substantial, whereas 30% state that their learning outcome improved slightly.

The respondents were asked to qualify their work with the quizzes in general, and the students gave us statements such as:

- "Very educative and interesting to see the groups quizzes"
- "The idea with quizzes is very good. Should be extended to all lectures"
- "A good way to recap a topic"
- "You remember the questions you prepare"

- “Funny and different way to learn”
- “Educative to prepare quizzes, less rewarding to answer the other groups quizzes”

As is evident from table 1 and the statements above, the students found the learning activities very educational, i.e. Quizry underpins Tinto’s self-efficacy and perception of curriculum.

Through our observations during teaching sessions, the following came to surface:

- All Quizry groups were inclusive during the teamwork
- In the process of making Quizry, students started revisiting teaching materials such as books and assignments
- Some students started out by resisting the learning process, Quizry, with comments such as “why do we have to make a quiz, we are used to instructors making quizzes?”
- Students found it difficult to phrase valid questions and plausible answers
- The quality of the various Quizries was to a large extent dependent on the time students spent both preparing at home and in class
- Tendency to cut corners and preference for easier parts of the topic
- The teamwork was at times challenged by the fact that some students were not well-prepared or did not attend class that day
- By the end of the semester, students increasingly focused on exams and less on working on Quizry
- As instructors we experienced the need to continuously frame Quizry in order to maintain students’ focus and motivation on the process

The Learning Management System used is DTU Learn/Brighspace, which has multiple possibilities to set up quizzes, but also lacks some features which would have been beneficial for our use. When the students had answered a quiz question, the students were taken to the next question without being told whether their answer was right or wrong. The same was the case when finalizing the quiz. This resulted in some students working around the system; they answered the quiz as intended but without delivering it in order to keep it open, so they could still see what they had answered.

It seems like the quiz module was originally designed for testing purposes and not as a didactical tool in itself. Answering the quiz is quite an independent and individual task for the student, and not until everybody had finished the quiz were we able to discuss answers and results in class. A didactical software tool such as Kahoot might have suited our purpose even better. The gamification and the possibility to take discussions after each question might have improved the process further, which actually was our initial idea.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

4.1 Discussion and suggestions for future research

During the project we have obtained some insights:

Formulating good MC questions is not easy and can be quite challenging. Lotte D. O'Neill [7] mentions several design errors, which should be avoided. For a student, who may only design MC questions once, and under strict time limitations as well, it is a difficult task. As part of the quality control, we had to go in and modify some of the questions and answers.

- The framing of the quiz work to the students at the beginning of the project could be repeated advantageously more in depth during the course. We observed that it was more difficult to maintain a few students' focus regarding the quiz work later in the process.
- Some students did not use sufficient time at home preparing the quiz questions, which resulted in some of the input to the quiz-responsible group was not of sufficient quality. As a consequence, instructors used more time than planned during and in between classes. The lack of engagement from some of the students due to not preparing the quiz questions at home influenced these students' learning.

We would like to research further the impact of engaging students on self-efficacy and sense of belonging. Moreover, we are very interested in examining to which extent students' course expectations influence their quiz work, e.g. students' resistance to learner-centered-teaching (LCT) and lastly reasons, including socio-economic, why students fail to prepare. We would like to conduct such research with a higher qualitative focus, e.g. semi-structured interviews and various observation methods to an even greater extent.

4.2. Conclusion

Our study results show that an extensive part of students experienced improved learning outcomes compared to traditional teaching.

It is evident from our study that students who work with Quizry will strengthen their knowledge and competencies; however, it is also clear that the students putting most effort into Quizry are the ones who obtain the highest learning outcomes. Furthermore, the students appreciate the opportunity of various didactical tools. The study shows that Quizry enhanced the students perception of curriculum, self-efficacy and sense of belonging.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jakobsen, A. et. al. (1999), Kvalitetsudviklingsprojektet "Faglig Sammenhæng", hovedrapport. CDM's skriftserie nr. 1, DTU
- [2] Krathwohl, D. R. (2002), A revision of Bloom's taxonomy; An overview. *Theory into practice*, 41(4), 212-218
- [3] Brousseau, G. (1997), *Theory of Didactical Situations in Mathematics*. Kluwer Academic Publishers
- [4] Tinto, V. (2017), Through the Eyes of Students, *Journal of College Students Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, Vol. 19, No. 3. pp. 254-269
- [5] Leth Andersen, H. et al (2016), Eksamen og eksamensformer – betydning og betydning. *Samfundslitteratur*, 2. Udgave
- [6] Larsen, S. (1998), *Den ultimative formel for effektive læreprocesser*, Hellerup; Steen Larsen
- [7] O'Neill, L.D. (2021), Multiple choice-spørgsmål i undervisningen, *Dansk Universitetspædagogisk Tidsskrift*, årgang 16, nr. 30